

Transition metal complexes of dehydroacetic acid chalcone : Synthesis, spectral, thermal and fungicidal study

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Abstract : Transition metal complexes containing bidentate O, O donor ligand, i.e. 3-[3-(4-chloro-phenyl)-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-pyran-2-one derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (dehydroacetic acid) and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, conductometry, thermal analysis, magnetic, IR, ¹H NMR, UV-Vis, X-ray diffraction and fungicidal study. From the analytical and thermal data, the stoichiometry of the complexes has been found to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand). Distorted octahedral geometry for Cu^{II} complex and octahedral geometries for Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are proposed. The kinetic parameters (*n*, *E*, *A*, ΔS and ΔG) from thermal analysis, for the Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes have been estimated. The X-ray diffraction suggests monoclinic crystal system for Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} complexes. The ligand and their metal complexes have been screened *in vitro* for their antifungal activities against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Curvularia lunata* and *Penicillium notatum*.

Keywords : Chalcone, dehydroacetic acid, transition metal complexes, thermal analysis.

Unsaturated ketones are gaining importance as reactive intermediates and are used to obtain the biologically important heterocycles. This class of compounds exhibits wide spectrum of pharmaceutical and biological properties¹⁻³. It has been shown that the prime cause of these activities, is the presence of α , β unsaturated ketonic system⁴. The fungal and bacterial activities of such unsaturated ketones are also enhanced by the substitution of halogen groups⁵. It is well known from the literature that dehydroacetic acid (3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran 2,4(3H)-dione), a biologically active compound has shown to have good antibiotic and antifungal effects, besides showing strong antiseptic properties⁶⁻⁸. It has also been used to enhance vitamin 'C' stability in vegetables, food processing and as a preservative⁹. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize some metal complexes of dehydroacetic acid chalcone containing α , β unsaturated ketonic system and investigate their bonding, thermal, spectral and fungicidal characteristics.

Results and discussion

The elemental analysis show 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry for all the complexes (Fig. 1). The analyti-

cal data of the ligand and the complexes are given in Table 1. It corresponds well with the general formula $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]$, where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}; $[ML_2(Cl)(H_2O)]$, where M = Fe^{III} and $[ML_2(H_2O)_2].2H_2O$, where M = Ni^{II} and L = C₁₅H₁₁O₄Cl. The presence of water

Fig. 1. The proposed structure of the complexes : X = H₂O; when M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, X = Cl⁻; when M = Fe^{III}.

Table 1. Analytical, molar conductance and characteristic IR frequencies of the ligand and its metal complexes

Compd.	Color	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Mol. wt.	Decom. temp. (°C)	λ_m (Mho cm ² mol ⁻¹)	IR frequencies (cm ⁻¹)				
		C	H	Cl	M				vC=O (lactone)	vC=O (acetyl carbonyl)	vC=O (phenolic)	vM-O	
Ligand C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₄ Cl	Light orange	61.48 (61.98)	3.92 (3.81)	12.01 (12.20)	-	290.7	161	-	3112 (b)	1715 (m)	1676 (m)	1232 (s)	
[C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ Cl ₂ Mn] complex	Yellowish brown	53.62 (53.74)	3.427 (3.607)	10.32 (10.58)	8.020 (8.194)	670.5	252	7.1	3379 (b)	1711 (m)	1648 (m)	1282 (m)	529 (m) 556 (m)
[C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₉ Cl ₃ Fe] complex	Dark brown	53.02 (52.30)	3.312 (3.218)	14.95 (15.46)	8.007 (8.107)	688.8	230	8.2	3373 (b)	1716 (m)	1643 (m)	1287 (m)	496 (m) 538 (m) 595 (m)
[C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ Cl ₂ Co] complex.	Light brown	53.99 (53.43)	3.496 (3.586)	9.92 (10.52)	8.432 (8.738)	674.4	>300	13.7	3375 (b)	1710 (m)	1630 (m)	1285 (m)	530 (m) 593 (m)
[C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ Cl ₂ Ni].2H ₂ O complex	Pale green	52.86 (53.44)	3.602 (3.587)	9.83 (10.53)	8.637 (8.705)	728.2	>300	10.1	3377 (b)	1716 (m)	1654 (m)	1286 (m)	498 (m) 534 (m)
[C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ Cl ₂ Cu] complex	Green	52.96 (53.06)	3.499 (3.562)	10.12 (10.45)	9.102 (9.357)	679.1	226	11.1	3374 (b)	1721 (m)	1650 (m)	1283 (m)	493 (m) 549 (m)

of crystallization and lattice water is confirmed by TGA-DTA analysis. The low conductance of the chelate solution supports the non electrolytic nature of the metal complexes.

IR spectra : Important spectral bands for the ligand and their metal complexes are presented in Table 1. The IR spectrum of the ligand shows bands at 3112, 1715, 1676 and 1232 cm^{-1} assignable to νOH (intramolecular hydrogen bonded), $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ (lactone carbonyl), $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ (acetyl carbonyl) and $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ (phenolic) respectively¹⁰. In the IR spectra of all the metal chelates, no band is observed in the region 3112 cm^{-1} , suggesting the cleavage of intramolecularly hydrogen bonded OH and participation of oxygen of phenolic group in coordination¹¹. This is supported by an upward shift in $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ (phenolic)¹¹ to the extent 30–60 cm^{-1} . The $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ (acetyl carbonyl) is shifted to the lower energy with respect to the free ligand, suggesting the participation of $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ (acetyl carbonyl) in coordination¹². In the IR spectra of all the chelates a broad trough appeared around 3500–3200 cm^{-1} which is due to νOH of coordinated water. This is supported by the presence of non ligand band¹³ around 820–840 cm^{-1} . The presence of new bands in the region 600–450 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ vibrations¹⁴.

¹H NMR spectrum : The ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand was recorded in CDCl_3 . The spectrum shows peaks at $\delta = 2.28$ (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 5.96 (1H, s, C_5-H) for dehydroacetic acid moiety, $\delta = 7.2-8.32$ (7H, m) for aromatic and olefinic protons and $\delta = 17.75$ (1H, s, C_4-OH) due to strong intramolecular phenolic hydrogen.

Magnetic moment and electronic absorption spectra : The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complex exhibit bands at 17513, 19724 and 25707 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{G})$, ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{G})$ and ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{1g}$, indicating an octahedral configuration¹⁵ around Mn^{II} . The octahedral geometry of Mn^{II} is further confirmed by the value of magnetic moment (5.96 B.M.).

Three electronic transitions are observed at 14619, 21786 and 24691 cm^{-1} for Fe^{III} complex, which are assigned to ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{G})$, ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{G})$ and ${}^6\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}_g(\text{G})$. These bands are consistent with an octahedral complex of Fe^{III} and confirmed by the value of magnetic moment (5.82 B.M.).

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complex exhibit three bands at 9596, 18450 and 24213 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ respectively, indicating octahedral configuration around Co^{II} ion. The magnetic moment of Co^{II} complex is 4.67 B.M. The calculated spectral parameters ν_2/ν_1 , $10Dq$, B , β and ligand field stabilizing

energy (LFSE) have values 1.92, 8854 cm^{-1} , 925 cm^{-1} , 0.95 and 25.29 kcal mol^{-1} respectively, which are in good agreement with the reported values of octahedral Co^{II} complex¹⁶. The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} exhibit three bands at 9398, 15384 and 24154 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ respectively. The ligand field parameters ν_2/ν_1 , $10Dq$, B , β and LFSE have values 1.65, 9395 cm^{-1} , 767.5 cm^{-1} , 0.73 and 26.85 kcal mol^{-1} . These values as well as the magnetic moment value (2.79 B.M.) support the octahedral geometry of Ni^{II} complex.

The Cu^{II} complex consists of a broad band at 14388 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^2\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ character of distorted octahedral stereochemistry with D_{4h} geometry¹⁷. Beside, the above band, the band observed at 25316 cm^{-1} may be assigned due to charge transfer. The LFSE of Cu^{II} complex is 40.6 kcal mol^{-1} . The obtained value of LFSE determines the stability of the complexes and follows the order in terms of metal ions $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$. This stability order is in fair agreement with the order reported¹⁸.

Thermal analysis : The Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are chosen for determining the kinetic parameters i.e. n (order of reaction), E (energy of activation), A (pre-exponential factor), ΔS (entropy change) and ΔG (free energy change). The different decomposition stages of the complexes with percentage losses are represented in Table 2. Evaluation of the mechanism of reaction from non-isothermal methods has been discussed by Sestak and Berggren¹⁹ and Satava²⁰. The linear plots are constructed for the different decomposition steps using nine mechanistic equations proposed by Satava and correlation coefficient values are evaluated. The best linear plot obtained for each of the decomposition stages is chosen as the mechanism of the reaction, in which the correlation coefficient value is close to unity. Along with the mechanistic equation, non-mechanistic method suggested by Coats-Redfern method²¹ have also been used for comparison. By using different values of order of reaction, straight line was fitted by regression. The highest value of r (correlation coefficient) gave the correct value of ' n '. From the slope and intercept, E and A values were calculated. Using E and A values, the values of ΔS and ΔG were determined (Table 2).

In the TG curve of Mn^{II} complex, the first step shows a steep slope between 150–200 °C with a mass loss of 6.0% (calcd. 5.37%), indicates the removal of two molecules of coordinated water, an endothermic peak in the range 150–200 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{min}} = 168$ °C) in DTA corresponds to dehydration step. The anhydrous compound

Table 2. Calculation of kinetic parameters by mechanistic equations (M.E.) and Coats-Redfern (C.R.) methods

Complex	Step	ΔT (°C)	Mass loss (%) Obs. (Calcd.)	Probable species	Method	n	E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	A (s ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Reaction mechanism
Mn ^{II} complex	1	150	6.0 (5.37)	Two coordinated	C.R.	0.98	105.5	1.0×10^{11}	-37.38	107.5	F ₁
		- 200		H ₂ O	M.E.	-	105.56	1.9×10^{10}	-51.14	108.3	
	2	200	38.0 (36.98)	Non- coordinated	C.R.	0.92	66.55	6.4×10^5	-138.2	74.91	F ₁
		- 350		part	M.E.	-	67.42	1.5×10^5	-150.1	76.50	
	3	400	45.0 (46.83)	Coordinated	C.R.	1.29	5.154	0.0413	-274.7	19.63	D ₃
		- 750		part of ligand	M.E.	-	8.983	0.0104	-286.2	24.05	
Fe ^{III} complex	1	150	7.5 (7.7)	One H ₂ O and	C.R.	1.1	97.60	1.7×10^{10}	-52.13	100.31	F ₁
		- 190		one Cl ⁻ ion	M.E.	-	97.31	2.9×10^9	-66.71	100.78	
	2	200	36.0 (36.93)	Non- coordinated	C.R.	1.02	13.79	0.4266	-257.2	30.89	F ₁
		- 370		part	M.E.	-	13.68	0.0776	-271.4	31.73	
	3	450	38.5 (-)	Coordinated	C.R.	1.1	6.621	0.0315	-283.6	39.81	D ₂
		- 975		part of ligand	M.E.	-	5.492	2.48×10^6	-362.12	47.87	
Cu ^{II} complex	1	150	6.0 (5.34)	Two coordinated	C.R.	0.92	52.69	1.4×10^4	-168.5	61.78	F ₁
		- 200		H ₂ O	M.E.	-	52.79	2.8×10^3	-182.1	62.61	
	2	250	38.0 (36.98)	Non- coordinated	C.R.	1.35	3.022	12.16	-230.2	47.20	D ₂
		- 475		part	M.E.	-	31.93	0.010	-288.9	53.23	
	3	475	45.0 (46.83)	Coordinated	C.R.	1.16	9.685	0.0856	-274.1	37.64	D ₃
		- 950		part of ligand	M.E.	-	19.55	0.0562	-277.6	47.86	
Ni ^{II} complex	1	30-	7.5 (7.42)	Three lattice	C.R.	0.97	5.523	0.0241	-276.1	16.52	F ₁
		125		H ₂ O	M.E.	-	5.412	0.00424	-291.2	16.98	

Table-2 (contd.)

	2	135	5.0	Two coordinated	C.R.	0.98	9.040	0.0796	-268.1	23.50	F ₁
		-	(5.33)	H ₂ O	M.E.	-	9.060	0.1515	-282.9	23.79	
		185									
	3	325	34.17	Non-coordinated	C.R.	0.88	39.92	76.06	-215.2	56.30	F ₁
		-	(36.93)	part	M.E.	-	41.16	18.99	-226.7	58.39	
		425									
	4	350	43.0	Coordinated	C.R.	0.87	10.22	0.0830	-275.2	41.27	D ₁
		-	(43.13)	part of ligand	M.E.	-	8.363	0.0219	-286.2	40.65	
		475									
Cu ^{II} complex	1	150	6.0	Two coordinated	C.R.	1.20	177.7	4.9 × 10 ¹⁹	128.8	170.9	F ₁
		-	(5.30)	H ₂ O	M.E.	-	176.7	7.0 × 10 ¹⁸	112.7	170.7	
		185									
	2	185	36.0	Non-coordinated	C.R.	1.21	42.44	8.9 × 10 ²	-192.8	54.10	F ₁
		-	(36.52)	part	M.E.	-	41.06	1.1 × 10 ²	-209.9	53.76	
		300									
	3	325	45.5	Coordinated	C.R.	1.19	5.462	0.0290	-282.3	37.71	D ₃
		-	(46.24)	part of ligand	M.E.	-	13.21	0.0170	-286.8	39.86	
		850									

in second step decomposes within a short temperature range from 200–350 °C with a 38% mass loss (calcd. 36.98%), an exotherm between 200 and 400 °C with $\Delta T_{\max} = 250$ °C in DTA. This step may be attributed to the removal of non-coordinated part of the ligand i.e. aromatic ring including beta carbon of the unsaturated ketonic group of the ligand (C₁₄H₁₀Cl₂). The rate controlling processes of first two steps are found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F₁). The third step corresponds to the decomposition of coordinated part of the ligand and in the range of 400–750 °C with a mass loss 45% (calcd. 46.83%). A broad endotherm in DTA is observed for this step. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be three dimensional diffusion with spherical symmetry (Jander equation) (D₃). The mass of the final residue corresponds to stable MnO, 11.0% (calcd. 10.59%).

The TG curve of the Fe^{III} complex shows three stage decomposition. The first stage involves the loss of one water molecule and one chloride ion at 179.0 °C (obs. 7.5%, calcd. 7.7%). This is supported by DT curve having one sharp endothermic peak. The second stage involves the loss of non coordinated part i.e. aromatic ring including beta carbon of the unsaturated ketonic group of the ligand in the temperature range 210–360 °C (obs. 36%, calcd. 36.93%). The rate controlling processes of first two steps are found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F₁). The third stage of decomposition is in the range of 450–960 °C (obs. 38.5%), may be attributed to oxidative degradation of remaining part of the ligand. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be two-dimensional diffusion, cylindrical symmetry (D₂). The mass of the final residue does not correspond to any stoichiometry.

The thermal decomposition profile of Co^{II} complex shows no weight loss up to 150 °C. The mass loss of 6.0% (calcd. 5.34%) is observed in the range 150–200 °C. An endothermic peak between 140–225 °C (ΔT_{\min} = 170 °C), correspond to loss of two molecules of water. The rate controlling process of this step is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The second step decomposition is in between temperature 250 and 475 °C with 38% mass loss (calcd. 36.98%). A broad exothermic peak between 235–450 °C (ΔT_{\max} = 360 °C) in DTA, attributed to the removal of non-coordinating part of the ligand (C₁₄H₁₀Cl₂). The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be two-dimensional diffusion, cylindrical symmetry (D_2). The mass loss continues and follows slow decomposition of remaining part of the ligand 45% (calcd. 46.83%). A broad endotherm in DT curve is observed for this step. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be three dimensional diffusion with spherical symmetry (Jander equation) (D_3). The mass of the final residue corresponds to CoO, 11% (calcd. 11.11%).

In case of Ni^{II} complex, the TG curve of the complex shows four stage decomposition. The first stage in TG curve shows loss of three lattice water molecules in the temperature range 50–110 °C (obs. 7.5%, calcd. 7.42%), supported by DT curve having one sharp endothermic peak (57.44 °C). The second stage involves loss of two coordinated water molecules at 187.87 °C (obs. 5.0%, calcd. 5.33%). This is supported by DT curve having one sharp endothermic peak. The third stage of decomposition is rapid and in the range of 320–430 °C, may be attributed to non-coordinated part i.e. aromatic ring including beta carbon of the unsaturated ketonic group of the ligand (obs. 34.17%, calcd. 36.93%). The rate controlling processes of first three steps are found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The fourth stage of decomposition is in the range of 450–950 °C, may be attributed to the oxidative degradation of remaining part of the ligand. The rate controlling process of this step is found to be one-dimensional diffusion (D_1). The mass of the final residue correspond to NiO (obs. 10%, calcd. 10%).

In the TG curve of Cu^{II} complex, the mass loss starts from 100 °C and an inclined slope from 150–185 °C with a mass loss of 6.0% (calcd. 5.30%), indicates the removal of two molecules of coordinated water, an endothermic peak in the range 150–200 °C (ΔT_{\min} = 175 °C) in DTA corresponds to dehydration step. The rate controlling processes of first two steps are found to be

Table 3. XRD data of Fe^{III} complex

$2\theta_{\text{obs.}}$	$2\theta_{\text{calcd.}}$	$D_{\text{obs.}}$	$\sin^2\theta - \text{obs.}$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$\sin^2\theta - \text{calcd.}$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$h k l$	Relative intensity (%)
20.75	20.76	4.278	324.2	324.5	0 0 1	54.6
21.14	21.14	4.198	336.5	336.5	-1 1 1	56.3
22.85	22.87	3.887	392.6	392.9	0 2 1	41.3
23.07	23.08	3.852	399.9	400.1	2 0 0	33.3
25.28	25.26	3.519	479.1	478.4	0 3 1	100
28.71	28.71	3.106	614.8	615.3	0 6 0	86.6
32.64	32.64	2.741	789.7	787.8	-2 4 1	84.0
32.93	32.93	2.718	803.2	803.2	1 4 1	30.6
34.92	34.92	2.566	900.6	900.2	3 0 0	38.6
36.43	36.44	2.464	977.0	977.7	3 2 1	38.6
38.57	38.54	2.332	1090	1088	2 3 1	36.0
42.21	42.24	2.139	1296	1298	0 0 2	33.3
45.64	45.65	1.986	1504	1504	-4 0 1	30.6
49.07	49.09	1.855	1724	1725	0 5 2	30.6
58.29	58.29	1.582	2371	2371	-2 8 2	14.7

random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The mass loss continues in TG curve upto 300 °C with a mass loss 36% (calcd. 36.52%), an exothermic peak (ΔT_{\max} = 230 °C) in DTA may be attributed to the removal of non-coordinated part of the ligand. The third step corresponds to decomposition of coordinated part of the ligand and in the range of 325–850 °C with a mass loss 45.5% (calcd. 46.24%). A broad endotherm is observed for this step. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be three dimensional diffusion with spherical symmetry (Jander equation) (D_3). The mass of the final residue corresponds to CuO, 12.5% (calcd. 11.71%).

The order of the reaction for different decomposition stages is in between 0.88 to 1.35. The energy of activation shows a decreasing order. The negative values of ΔS show that the complexes are more ordered in the activated state than the reactants.

Powder X-ray diffraction : X-Ray diffraction pattern of complexes Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} are presented in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. The observed 2θ s are indexed and have been used for evaluating the calculated sin square theta and $2\theta_{\text{cal}}$ values for comparison. The diffractogram of Fe^{III} complex consist of fifteen reflections between 20° and 80° with maximum reflection $2\theta = 25.28^\circ$ corresponding to the value of $d = 3.5194 \text{ \AA}$, whereas the diffractogram of Cu^{II} complex consist of twelve reflections between 5° and 80° with maximum reflection at $2\theta =$

Table 4. XRD data of Cu^{II} complex

$2\theta_{\text{obs.}}$	$2\theta_{\text{calcd.}}$	$D_{\text{obs.}}$	$\sin^2\theta - \text{obs.}$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$\sin^2\theta - \text{calcd.}$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$h k l$	Relative intensity (%)
7.92	7.92	11.14	47.75	47.73	0 0 1	26.2
10.79	10.79	8.189	88.48	88.43	2 0 0	8.7
12.96	12.98	6.825	127.4	127.8	-2 0 1	14.6
13.79	13.80	6.414	144.2	144.4	2 0 1	20.2
22.00	22.01	4.036	364.2	364.6	-1 1 1	19.8
24.15	24.19	3.681	437.7	139.1	-1 0 3	15.3
25.55	25.57	3.482	489.1	489.8	0 1 2	21.1
28.86	28.86	3.090	621.2	621.2	5 0 1	10.8
32.68	32.69	2.737	791.7	791.9	-2 1 3	100
40.25	40.25	2.238	1183	1183	4 0 4	9.3
46.85	46.85	1.9374	1580	1580	-4 2 1	11.4
58.25	58.25	1.582	2369	2368	-2 0 7	15.3

32.68° corresponding to the value of $d = 2.737 \text{ \AA}$.

The diffractogram patterns of complexes with respect to their prominent peaks have been indexed by using computer software keeping in mind the characteristics of various symmetry systems, till a good fit could be obtained between observed and calculated sin square theta and 2θ values. The above indexed method also yielded miller indices (hkl) value. The unit cell parameters were calculated using the indexed data refined by weight fraction of the sample. In turn using this parameter, volume of unit cell was computed. The relative intensities corresponding to the prominent peaks have been calculated by normalizing them with respect to their maximum.

The comparison of value of observed and calculated sin square theta and 2θ , listed in Tables 3 and 4 reveals that there is good agreement between them on the basis of assumption of monoclinic crystal structure. The small differences in the observed ' d ' spacing can be attributed to difference in unit cell dimensions. The unit cell of the Cu^{II} complex yielded values for lattice constant $a = 16.4162 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 4.4553 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.1728 \text{ \AA}$ and unit cell volume $V = 815.51 \text{ \AA}^3$. The unit cell of the Fe^{III} complex yielded values for lattice constant $a = 8.0521 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 18.6317 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 4.4700 \text{ \AA}$ and unit cell volume $V = 641.45 \text{ \AA}^3$. In conjunction with these evaluated cell parameters, the condition such as $a \neq b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \delta = 90^\circ \neq \beta$ required for the samples to be monoclinic were tested and found to be satisfactory. Hence it is concluded that the complexes under study has monoclinic structure.

The experimental density values of the complexes were determined by using specific gravity method²². The

number of molecules (n) per unit cell were calculated by using equation $\rho = nm/NV$ and was found to be 2 for Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes, with this number, theoretical density has been computed. The experimental and theoretical density values of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} are 2.733, 2.765 and 3.508, 3.566 g cm⁻³. When experimental density value of the complexes compared with the theoretical density value, it is found that there is good agreement within the limits of experimental errors. The particle size²³, porosity of Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} complexes were found to be 595.77 Å, 6.81% and 316.94 Å, 10.39% respectively.

Fungicidal activity : To evaluate fungicidal activity of the ligands and their corresponding metal complexes, their effect on the growth of *Aspergillus flavus*, *Curvularia lunata* and *Penicillium notatum* was studied. The ligand and their corresponding metal chelates in DMF were screened by mycelia dry weight method¹¹ *in vitro* for their fungicidal activity in glucose nitrate media. The ligand exhibited 20–25 and 30–35% inhibition for 125 and 250 ppm concentration respectively. It is observed that the metal complexes show enhanced antifungal activity as compared to the ligand. This is because of chelation, which reduces the polarity of metal ion due to partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and also due to delocalization of pi electrons over whole chelate ring. Thus chelation increases lipophilic character in the complexes and results in the enhancement of activity²⁴. The inhibition by metal complexes has been increased by 30–65% and 40–70% for 125 and 250 ppm concentration respectively. The order of inhibition with respect to metal ions is Cu > Co > Ni > Mn > Fe.

Experimental

Dehydroacetic acid and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde used for the preparation of ligand were from Merck and Aldrich respectively. Metal chlorides used for the complex preparation were from B.D.H. The carbon, hydrogen and sulphur content in each sample were measured on Perkin-Elmer (2400) CHNS analyzer. IR spectra (nujol) in the range of 4000–450 cm⁻¹ were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (C-75430) IR spectrometer. The AAS, TGA-DTA and XRD were recorded on Perkin-Elmer PE-Analyst 300, TA/SDT-2960 and Philips 3701/Philips 1701 respectively. The UV-Vis spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of complexes were carried out using a Gouy balance at room temperature and Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. Molar conductivity was measured on an Elico CM180 conductivity meter with a

dip-type cell using 10^{-3} M solution of complexes in DMF.

Synthesis of ligand : A solution of 3.4 g (0.02 mol) of dehydroacetic acid, 10 drops of piperidine and 2.8 g (0.02 mol) of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde in 25 ml chloroform was refluxed for 8–10 h. 10 ml of the chloroform-water azeotrope mixture was separated by distillation. Crystals of product were separated on slow evaporation of the remaining chloroform and recrystallised from ethanol.

Synthesis of metal complexes : To a chloroform solution (30 ml) of the ligand (10 mmol), methanolic solution (20 ml) of metal chloride (5 mmol) was added with constant stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained around 7.5 by adding 10% methanolic solution of ammonia. It was then refluxed for 2 h. The resulting metal complex was filtered in hot condition and washed with chloroform, methanol, pet-ether and dried over calcium chloride in vacuum desiccator.

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